

The Unjournal

Evaluation Summary and Metrics: “Pharmaceutical Pricing and R&D as a Global Public Good”

Evaluator 1 Evaluator 2 Tabare Capitan

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ABSTRACT

We organized two evaluations of the paper: "Pharmaceutical Pricing and R&D as a Global Public Good" [1]. This work considers global drug pricing and whether, relative to the United States, the rest of the world underpays for pharmaceuticals, underfunding R&D as a public good. The authors quantify cross-country differences in drug prices, benchmark these against willingness-to-pay thresholds, and discuss the implications for international pricing negotiations. The evaluators agree that the paper tackles an important problem with the potential for real-world policy impact, positive or negative. Both were moderately critical of the paper, providing overall percentile ratings of 51 and 31, i.e., at or below the median "relative to all serious research in the same area that you have encountered in the last three years." Both evaluators questioned the practical credibility of the claim that ROW "should" pay more, noting the complexities of domestic U.S. pricing systems, insurance structures, and bargaining power. The evaluators' feedback offers a constructive path forward: clarifying empirical claims, grounding recommendations in realistic policy mechanisms, and ensuring transparency about limitations. To read these evaluations, please see the links below.

Evaluations

1. [Evaluator 1](#)

2. [Evaluator 2](#)

Overall ratings

We asked evaluators to provide overall assessments as well as ratings for a range of specific criteria.

I. Overall assessment (See footnote¹)

II. Journal rank tier, normative rating (0-5): On a 'scale of journals', what 'quality of journal' should this be published in?² Note: 0= lowest/none, 5= highest/best.

	Overall assessment (0-100)	Journal rank tier, normative rating (0-5)
Evaluator 1	51	2.0
Evaluator 2	30	2.5

See "[Metrics](#)" below for a more detailed breakdown of the evaluators' ratings across several categories. To see these ratings in the context of all Unjournal ratings, with some analysis, see our [data presentation here](#).³

See [here](#) for the current full evaluator guidelines, including further explanation of the requested ratings.

Evaluation summaries

Anonymous evaluator 1

This paper provides a comprehensive analysis of pharmaceutical research and development (R&D) as a global public good, highlighting the contributions made by various countries. It successfully gathers valuable data and employs innovative methods to calculate marginal costs. However, the empirical approach could be improved by addressing omitted variable bias and incorporating general equilibrium effects. Furthermore, the conceptual framework could be broadened to include dynamic factors and supply-side considerations.

Anonymous evaluator 2

Strengths and achievements:

1. Applies a classic public-good model to explain why U.S. drug prices exceed those in ROW and remain below the global optimum
 2. Empirical markups dispel the notion that non-U.S. markets fully free-ride
- Positive GDP–price correlation aligns with theoretical predictions

Critiques, limitations, and suggestions:

1. Empirical tests are correlational and could have alternate explanations
2. Theoretical results rest on the assumption of optimal centralized government action
3. Policy prescriptions likely warrant further empirical validation

Metrics

Ratings

[See here](#) for details on the categories below, and the guidance given to evaluators.

	Evaluator 1		Evaluator 2	
	Anonymous		Anonymous	
Rating category	Rating (0-100)	90% CI (0-100)*	Rating (0-100)	90% CI (0-100)*
Overall assessment ⁴	51	(35, 65)	30	(10, 50)

Claims, strength, characterization of evidence ⁵	20	(5, 40)	70	(50, 90)
Advancing knowledge and practice ⁶	85	(75, 95)	25	(10, 40)
Methods: Justification, reasonableness, validity, robustness ⁷	55	(35, 75)	70	(60, 90)
Logic & communication ⁸	70	(55, 85)	80	(70, 90)
Open, collaborative, replicable ⁹	100	(100, 100)	100	(100, 100)
Real-world relevance 10 , 11	95	(89, 100)	35	(20, 70)
Relevance to global priorities ¹² , ¹³	95	(89, 100)	35	(20, 70)

Journal ranking tiers

[See here](#) for more details on these tiers.

	Evaluator 1		Evaluator 2	
	Anonymous		Anonymous	
Judgment	Ranking tier (0-5)	90% CI	Ranking tier (0-5)	90% CI
On a 'scale of journals', what 'quality of journal' <i>should</i> this be published in?	2.0	(1.0, 3.0)	2.5	(1.5, 3.1)

What ‘quality journal’ do you expect this work <i>will</i> be published in?	2.0	(1.0, 3.0)	N/A	N/A
See here for more details on these tiers.	<p><i>We summarize these as:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 0.0: Marginally respectable/Little to no value • 1.0: OK/Somewhat valuable • 2.0: Marginal B-journal/Decent field journal • 3.0: Top B-journal/Strong field journal • 4.0: Marginal A-Journal/Top field journal • 5.0: A-journal/Top journal 			

Claim identification and assessment (summary)

For the full discussions, see the corresponding sections in each linked evaluation.

	Main research claim ¹⁴	Belief in claim ¹⁵
Evaluator 1 Anonymous	<p>“For these reasons, US officials could raise these issues at international negotiations and advocate for higher prices than presently set in high-income ROW 35 countries. A multi-country agreement in this direction would represent a serious effort to support improved world health.”</p>	<p>Not fully supported from an economic or econometric standpoint. The framework cannot accurately predict how price increases in the rest of the world would influence global innovation, access, or welfare.</p>
Evaluator 2 Anonymous	<p>[Recovered from report]</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. ... “U.S. drug prices are higher than those in the ROW because the U.S. internalizes the impact of prices on R&D more than the ROW. 2. “drug prices in <i>both the U.S. and ROW</i> do not adequately incentivize R&D—though ROW prices are still higher than marginal cost, thus generating some R&D incentives.” 	

Evaluation manager's discussion

Why we chose this paper

We selected this paper because it tackles an important and controversial policy question: whether the rest of the world underpays for pharmaceuticals relative to the United States, potentially underfunding global pharmaceutical R&D as a public good. The authors quantify cross-country differences in drug prices, benchmark these against willingness-to-pay thresholds, and discuss the implications for international pricing negotiations. Framing pharmaceutical innovation explicitly as a public good is both timely and potentially impactful, especially given ongoing debates about equitable access, global health priorities, and incentives for innovation.

How we chose the evaluators

We deliberately paired two complementary perspectives. One evaluator has domain expertise in pharmaceutical markets, health economics, and global pricing policy. The other has strong empirical and econometric experience but is not a domain specialist. This mix was chosen to ensure the paper was evaluated both on its economic modeling and empirical strategy, and on its policy relevance, plausibility of its assumptions, and broader health-system context.

Author engagement

The authors were aware of our process but chose not to engage. As always, we invite their future response which we can share here.

Issues meriting further consideration

The evaluations highlight that while the paper explores an important question, several core claims require closer scrutiny. Both evaluators questioned the practical credibility of the claim that ROW "should" pay more, noting the complexities of domestic U.S. pricing systems, insurance structures, and bargaining power. One evaluator flagged the risk of the analysis being used to justify higher prices without sufficient attention to market failures or mechanisms for coordination. The other noted that some key literature (e.g., on willingness-to-pay benchmarks) was not fully integrated or cited. Overall, the evaluations suggest that clarifying these assumptions and better addressing real-world complexities would strengthen the paper and mitigate risks of misinterpretation.

Conclusion

This evaluation process confirms that the paper tackles an important problem with the potential for real-world policy impact, positive or negative. The evaluators' feedback offers a constructive path forward: clarifying empirical claims, grounding recommendations in realistic policy mechanisms, and ensuring transparency about

limitations. We see this as exactly the kind of discussion The Unjournal aims to support, helping authors refine their work for maximum rigor and relevance.

References

[1] Frech, H., Pauly, M., Comanor, W., & Martinez, J. (2023). *Pharmaceutical Pricing and R&D as a Global Public Good*. National Bureau of Economic Research. <https://doi.org/10.3386/w31272>

Footnotes

1. We asked them to rank this paper "heuristically" as a percentile "relative to all serious research in the same area that you have encountered in the last three years." We requested they "consider all aspects of quality, credibility, importance to knowledge production, and importance to practice. [↵](#)

2. See ranking tiers discussed [here](#). [↵](#)

3. Note: if you are reading this before, or soon after this has been publicly released, the ratings from this paper may not yet have been incorporated into that data presentation. [↵](#)

4.

Judge the quality of the research heuristically. Consider all aspects of quality, credibility, importance to knowledge production, and importance to practice.

[↵](#)

5. "Do the authors do a good job of (i) stating their main questions and claims, (ii) providing strong evidence and powerful approaches to inform these, and (iii) correctly characterizing the nature of their evidence?"

This was on the newer form only [↵](#)

6.

To what extent does the project contribute to the field or to practice, particularly in ways that are directly or indirectly relevant to global priorities and impactful interventions?

[↵](#)

7. Are methods clearly justified and explained? Are methods and their underlying assumptions reasonable? Are the results likely to be robust to changes in the assumptions? Have the authors avoided bias and questionable research practices? [↵](#)

8. Are concepts clearly defined? Is the reasoning transparent? Are conclusions consistent with the evidence (or formal proofs) presented? Are the data and/or analysis, including tables and figures, relevant to the argument? [↔](#)

9.

Would another researcher be able to replicate the analysis? Are the method and its details explained sufficiently? Is the source of the data clear? Is the data made as widely available as possible, with clear labeling and explanation? Do the authors provide resources that are likely to enable future research and meta-analysis?

[↔](#)

10.

Does the paper consider real-world relevance and deal with policy and implementation questions? Are the setup, assumptions, and focus realistic and relevant to practitioners?

[↔](#)

11.

The latter ratings were merged in the newer form

"Are the paper's chosen topic and approach likely to be useful to global priorities, cause prioritization, and high-impact interventions?"

"Does the paper consider real-world relevance and deal with policy and implementation questions? Are the setup, assumptions, and focus realistic? Do the authors report results that are relevant to practitioners? Do they provide useful quantified estimates (costs, benefits, etc.)?" [↔](#)

12. Are the paper's chosen topic and approach likely to be useful to global priorities, cause prioritization, and high-impact interventions? [↔](#)

13.

The latter ratings were merged in the newer form

"Are the paper's chosen topic and approach likely to be useful to global priorities, cause prioritization, and high-impact interventions?"

"Does the paper consider real-world relevance and deal with policy and implementation questions? Are the setup, assumptions, and focus realistic? Do the authors report results that are relevant to practitioners? Do they provide useful quantified estimates (costs, benefits, etc.)?" [↔](#)

14.

The evaluator was given the following instructions:

Identify the most important and impactful factual claim this research makes – e.g., a binary claim or a point estimate or prediction.

Please state the authors' claim precisely and quantitatively. Identify the source of the claim (i.e., cite the paper), and briefly mention the evidence underlying this. We encourage you to explain why you believe this claim is important, either here, or in the text of your report. ↵

15. Evaluators were asked: To what extent do you *believe* the claim you stated above? Feel free to express this either a. in terms of the probability of the claim being true, b. as a credible interval for the parameter being estimated, or c. however you feel comfortable. ↵

References

1. Frech, III, H. E., Mark V. Pauly, William S. Comanor, and Joseph R. Martinez. 2023. 'Pharmaceutical Pricing and R&D as a Global Public Good'. Working Paper. Working Paper Series. National Bureau of Economic Research. <https://doi.org/10.3386/w31272>. ↵

2.

10.3386/w31272

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